

Kinetic Studies of the Oxidation of Glucose by Ammoniacal Silver Nitrate

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The kinetics of the oxidation of glucose by ammoniacal silver nitrate has been studied. The rate of reaction is found to be first order with respect to silver nitrate, and it is particularly zero with respect to reductant. An increase in ammonia concentration increases the induction period. Study of the reaction at different temperatures give the values of temperature coefficient, energy and entropy of activation as 4.24, 26.38 Kcals and 10.71 e.u. respectively with the rate constants obtained after the expiry of induction period.

The fission of C-C bonds occurs with the progressive oxidation yielding mainly oxalic and glyceric acids. It is suggested that the oxidation occurs through enolic transformation of the carbonyl group.

The addition of an electrolyte like barium nitrate completely checks the formation of colloidal silver which has a catalysing influence on this reaction.

Silver ions as such are reduced to metallic silver by a few organic compounds like formic acid but ammoniacal silver nitrate, known as Tollen's reagent is reduced by several organic compounds chiefly having an aldehydic group. The reducing action of formic acid has been also ascribed due to the presence of an aldehydic group. The kinetics of the oxidation of formic acid with silver nitrate has been studied by Dhar¹, but the kinetics of reduction of ammoniacal silver nitrate, which provides a specific test for a number of reducing organic compounds viz., reducing sugars, tartaric acid etc., besides the aldehydes, have not been studied in detail. In this paper we have reported the kinetic study of glucose by ammoniacal silver nitrate to elucidate the mechanism of this reduction process.

EXPERIMENTAL

The standard solution of silver nitrate is prepared by direct weighing from a sample of A.R. quality and is kept in dark to avoid any photochemical reaction. Fresh solution of glucose (A.R. specification) is daily prepared by direct weighing and is standardised by a suitable method. A stock solution of potassium sulphocyanide is prepared from E. Merck sample and is standardised by Volhard's method. The ammonium hydroxide solution is standardised by acid-alkali titration.

The equivalent concentration of glucose in the reaction mixture is always kept in large excess over ammoniacal silver nitrate. The experimental technique, specially to maintain ammonia concentration constant, is similar to those already described in an earlier

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1. N. R. Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 707.

publication². The rate is followed by the volumetric estimation of silver nitrate by Volhard's method and is calculated after the expiry of the induction period. The results obtained are summarised in the following Table I in order to depict the nature of the progress of the reaction.

TABLE I

(Glucose) = 0.10M (Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M
Temperature = 30°

Time in minutes	Concentration of ammonium hydroxide		
	0.0832M	0.1040M	0.1248M
	$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$	$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$	$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$
40	15.68	15.58	—
50	14.86	13.87	10.82
60	14.48	13.10	10.27
70	14.32	12.98	—
75	—	—	10.98
80	14.30	12.81	—
90	14.38	13.00	10.43
100	—	—	10.59
Average	14.67	13.56	10.62

The values of rate constant k_1 indicate that the reaction follows first order law satisfactorily with respect to silver in solution, when these are calculated after the induction period, which lasted for first few minutes, is over.

Effect of Glucose Concentration : The reaction rates slightly decrease with the decrease of glucose concentration at lower temperature (Table II), while at a higher temperature (Table III) the specific rate constants remain practically the same.

TABLE II

(Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M (Ammonium Hydroxide) = 0.0832M
Temperature = 25°

Glucose concentrations	0.050M	0.10M	0.150M
$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$	6.188	7.030	8.950

TABLE III

(Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M (Ammonium Hydroxide) = 0.1040M
Temperature = 35°

Glucose concentrations	0.050M	0.10M	0.150M
$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$	21.53	21.49	23.88

TABLE VI

(Glucose) = 0.10M (Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M
 Temperature = 25°

Time in minutes	Concentrations of Ammonium Hydroxide		
	0.0624M $k_2 \times 10^4(\text{min}^{-1})$	0.1040M $k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$	0.1248M $k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$
40	24.90	5.008	—
50	23.37	—	—
55	—	5.138	3.642
60	21.96	—	—
70	—	4.903	3.583
90	22.77	5.009	3.688
110	24.08	5.006	3.706
130	—	5.333	4.130

It is also observed that with the decreasing concentration of ammonia, the induction period vanishes off and when the ammonia concentration is very low, i.e., it is just sufficient to dissolve silver hydroxide, the first order constants become large and gradually fall off; then the reaction appears to be second order with respect to silver in solution specially at lower temperatures. This is evidenced from the following Table VII (also Table VI).

TABLE VII

(Glucose) = 0.10M (Ammonium Hydroxide) = 0.0416M
 (Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M

Time in minutes	$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$ at 25°	$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$ at 30°	$k_1 \times 10^3(\text{min}^{-1})$ at 35°
4	—	—	139.4
6	—	80.52	135.5
8	—	—	132.4
10	—	78.25	134.0
15	29.23	76.28	142.2
20	26.50	69.34	—
25	—	61.01	—
30	25.92	55.46	—
40	22.91	—	—
50	19.84	—	—

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30	25.92	55.46	—
40	22.91	—	—
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The value of temperature coefficient, k_{t+10}/K_t , is calculated from the average values of first order constant of 0.10M glucose in the presence of 0.0832M, 0.1040M and 0.1248M ammonia and is found to be 4.24.

Energy and Entropy of Activation : The energy of activation, from the average first order constants of two temperatures 25° and 35°, in the presence of 0.0832M, 0.1040M and 0.1248M ammonia and 0.10M glucose, has been calculated and is found to be 26.377 Kcals. From this value, the entropy of activation comes out to be 10.71 e.u.

Effect of Electrolytes on the Reaction Rate : During the reduction of ammoniacal silver nitrate by glucose it is observed that colloidal silver appears first as apple yellow sol which gradually deepens to a deep blue or black coloured sol of silver which settles with difficulty but coagulable by an electrolyte. In the following Table VIII, the effect of potassium nitrate, barium nitrate and magnesium sulphate on the rate of reaction has been noted.

TABLE VIII

(Glucose) = 0.10M (Silver Nitrate) = 0.020M
(Ammonium Hydroxide) = 0.0416M, Temperature = 30°

Volume of reaction mixture taken out each time = 6.2 ml.

Time in minutes	Volume of 0.025M KCNS solution			
	nil	KNO ₃ 0.025M	Ba(NO ₃) ₂ 0.0025M	MgSO ₄ 0.005M
	in ml.	in ml.	in ml.	in ml.
0	4.96	4.96	4.96	4.96
6	3.06	3.34	—	3.78
10	2.44	2.70	4.20	—
12	1.94	2.16	—	2.94
15	1.58	1.80	—	2.64
20	1.24	1.44	3.98	2.26
25	0.94	1.26	—	—
30	—	1.14	—	1.96
40	—	—	3.76	1.54
60	—	—	3.70	—
90	—	—	3.58	—

It will be seen from the above table that the effect in decreasing the rate of reaction is more prominent with barium nitrate solution though the ionic strength of this electrolyte used in the experiment is lower than that of potassium nitrate and magnesium sulphate. However, it is well known that in negatively charged sol, the coagulating power is usually in the

order $Ba > Mg > K$. It also concludes that very fine particles of colloidal silver appearing *in situ* has some catalytic influence for the oxidation of glucose or organic substrate by ammoniacal silver nitrate. The larger size of colloidal particles have hardly any catalytic activity, because the introduction of colloidal silver prepared by reducing silver nitrate by hydroquinone and stabilized by potassium citrate did not appreciably catalyse this reaction. Hence, it is possible that to some extent the induction period observed in this reaction is due to autocatalysis by colloidal silver on its immediate formation and high dispersion, and hence by using an electrolyte as a coagulant, the reaction is considerably checked.

Determination of Equivalents : A measured excess (40.0 ml. of 0.10M) of silver nitrate solution is taken in a 300 ml. pyrex conical flask and to this 10.4 ml. 0.80M ammonium hydroxide solution is added so that it just dissolved all silver hydroxide. To this, 2.0 ml. of 0.050M glucose solution is introduced. The total volume of the reaction mixture is made 100 ml. by adding bidistilled water. The flask is then firmly corked and is kept for about a week at room temperature $30^\circ (\pm 2^\circ)$. When the period is over, the reaction mixture is filtered through sintered glass crucible and the clear filtrate is treated with concentrated nitric acid. The unreacted silver nitrate is titrated with a standard solution of potassium sulphocyanide using ferric alum indicator. A blank is also carried out under identical conditions except instead of glucose solution the same volume of distilled water is added. The difference in two potassium sulphocyanide readings gives the amount of silver nitrate consumed from which the equivalent is calculated.

The average of three experiments shows that the amount of silver ion consumed per mole of glucose is 11.97 equivalents of silver nitrate.

DISCUSSION

Monovalent silver and bivalent copper are the specific reagents for the oxidation of aldehydic group, in all cases oxidation occurring in alkaline medium. Monovalent silver in ammoniacal solution, known as Tollen's reagent, is more commonly used for identifying -CHO group than bivalent copper in alkaline tartarate or citrate solutions.

The main reaction of the oxidation of aldehydes may be represented by $R.CHO + 2Ag^+ \rightarrow R.COOH + 2Ag + 2H^+$. The action of H^+ ion in suppressing the oxidation may be said to be prominent, if the reaction is reversible. But, since the insoluble silver metal separates out as a precipitate, the reversibility is expected to be insignificant. It appears, therefore, that the function of alkaline medium is related with the mechanism of the oxidation. It has been suggested by Drummond and Waters that the oxidation of aldehydes by one electron abstracting oxidising agent, manganic pyrophosphate, occurs through the enolisation of the carbonyl group present in the aldehyde.

The ketonic group in the acetone is well known to undergo enolisation in acid medium making it reactive with halogens. Thus :

(1) and (2) represent the intermediate processes of enolisation. However, the ketonic group present in fructose is not halogenated in acid medium and it may be due to the fact that step (2) in the case of enolisation of the carbonyl group in an aldose or a ketose requires larger concentrations of an alkali. Hence, the rapid oxidation of a carbohydrate like glucose by monovalent silver can occur only in alkaline medium.

The whole process of enolisation involves the addition of proton and its subsequent removal by a base, and feebler the attachment of proton greater will be the acid concentration to effect the process (1) of enolisation and smaller concentration of the base will be required for the process (2). It is for this reason an aldehydic group attached with $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ group requires smaller hydrogen ion concentration for the first process and greater concentration of $-\text{OH}^-$ for its removal.

Drummond and Waters³ have reported that in the oxidation of the aldehydes by manganic pyrophosphate, the reaction is of zero order with respect to the oxidant and first order with respect to the organic substrate. Similar conclusion has been drawn by Ghosh *et al.*⁴ on the reduction of bivalent copper by some aldoses. The scheme suggested by Drummond and Waters which involves the oxidation through enolisation is noted below :—

which yields a mesomeric radical (7). Thus, the oxidative step (7) is facile, and if it is faster than forward step (5) with a base, the whole reaction will become zero order with respect to the oxidant.

In the present investigation it is found that the reduction of ammoniacal silver nitrate is either of first or second order, depending on the concentration of ammonia present in the system, and that the order with respect to organic substrate is zero. Thus, the various steps indicated in the mechanism suggested by Drummond and Waters do not appear to be applicable specially where the reaction is being carried out in alkaline solutions. It is therefore, suggested that in the present case the reaction occurs according to the following steps :

3. Wm. A. Waters, "Mechanism of the oxidation of organic compounds"; Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, (1964), p. 87.
4. M. P. Singh and S. Ghosh, *Z. Physik. Chem.* Liepzig 1955, **204**, 1; *ibid.*, 1956, **205**, 285; 1957, **207**, 198; 1961, **216**, 13.

It appears, therefore, that the reaction mechanism involves an enolisation and the function of ammonia is to speed up the reaction (9). Further, the kinetics of the reaction reveal that there is an induction period in the early stages of the reaction, and if the H^+ ion concentration is greatly depressed by adding larger quantities of ammonia, the reaction (8) is likely to be completely checked. Moreover, considerable amount of silver will appear as complex cations, $Ag(NH_3)^+$ and $Ag(NH_3)_2^+$.

It is also clear that in the presence of ammonia, the concentration of H^+ ion is low and hence, the reaction (8) may not be immediate and this will lead to an induction period. In reaction (9), the presence of ammonia will accelerate the forward reaction. The product, $R_2C = CHO$, is formed by silver ions (reaction 11) and therefore, its concentration is proportional to the concentration of silver ion, and if the reaction (12) is mainly the rate determining step, the reaction becomes second order with respect to silver ion. Hence, in the presence of smaller concentration of ammonia, we may assume that all the steps are fast as compared to the step (12). Whenever, larger concentration of ammonia are used, the step (11) is also slowed down because of the very low concentration of silver ions available from the ammino complex. In other words, in an excess of ammonia, the reaction will have sufficient induction period and will appear to be unimolecular or even less with respect to silver ion.

The determination of equivalents of silver oxidising a mole of glucose indicates that the reaction proceeds further than the acid produced by relation (13). It is noted that a hydroxy acid like tartaric is rapidly oxidized by ammoniacal silver nitrate possibly through the coordinated complex and it appears that the hydroxy acid produced from the first product of the oxidation of the carbohydrate by ammoniacal silver nitrate undergoes oxidation yielding oxalic and glyceric acids.

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